

Information Security Policy

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Revision History

Version	Date	Author	Description of Changes
1.0	03/15/2026	Stefan Krauss (ISM)	Initial approved version

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1. Purpose

The purpose of this document is to establish the information security policies for protecting the confidentiality, integrity, and availability of CasePilot LLC's information assets, and to formalize the organization's commitment to establishing, implementing, maintaining, and continuously improving an Information Security Management System (ISMS).

2. Scope

This policy applies to all employees, contractors, and third parties who access, process, or manage CasePilot LLC's information assets or information systems. It covers all information assets, information systems, and business processes that fall within the defined scope of the organization's Information Security Management System (ISMS).

3. Commitment

"We, the Executive Leadership, commit to providing the necessary leadership, direction, and resources to support the effective operation and continual improvement of the ISMS.

We recognize the importance of information security and the protection of our information assets.

We are committed to satisfying all applicable legal, regulatory, and contractual requirements related to information security, and to establishing, implementing, maintaining, and continually improving an effective Information Security Management System (ISMS)."

4. Information Security Principles

The organization establishes the following principles to guide the protection of information assets and the operation of the Information Security Management System (ISMS):

Risk-based approach: Information security decisions are based on the identification, assessment, and treatment of risks to the organization.

Business alignment: Information security supports and enables business objectives, rather than restricting operational effectiveness.

Accountability: Information security responsibilities are clearly assigned, and all personnel are accountable for the protection of information assets within their control.

Compliance: The organization commits to complying with applicable legal, regulatory, contractual, and internal information security requirements.

Continuous improvement: The ISMS is continuously reviewed and improved to ensure its ongoing effectiveness in response to internal and external changes.

5. Roles and Responsibilities

The organization's information security governance structure aims to ensure clear oversight, accountability, coordination, and effective operation of the ISMS.

The Executive Leadership holds accountability for information security, with the CEO acting as the primary accountable sponsor of the ISMS. While the Information Security Manager ensures that the ISMS achieves its intended outcomes.

All personnel, including employees, contractors, and third parties acting on behalf of the organization, are responsible for understanding and adhering to this Information Security Policy and all related information security policies, procedures, and controls.

Specific roles, responsibilities, and authorities related to the Information Security Management System (ISMS) are formally defined, documented, and maintained in the document "Information Security Roles and Responsibilities (FWR-05)."

6. Information Security Objectives

Information security objectives are established to support the organization's strategic direction and to ensure the effective operation and continual improvement of the Information Security Management System (ISMS).

Objectives are defined to be specific, measurable, achievable, relevant, and time-bound and are documented and maintained in the controlled document "Information Security Objectives (FRW-04)."

7. Governance & Compliance

7.1. Communication & Awareness

This Information Security Policy shall be communicated to all employees, contractors, and relevant third parties.

The organization ensures that personnel are aware of their information security responsibilities and receive appropriate training and awareness to support the effective operation of the ISMS.

7.2. Review

This policy shall be reviewed at least annually, or upon significant changes to the organization, its risk environment, or applicable legal and regulatory requirements.

7.3. Exceptions

Any exception to this policy must be formally documented, justified based on business or operational needs.

Approved exceptions shall be subject to risk assessment and periodic review.

7.4. Non-Compliance

Failure to comply with this policy may result in disciplinary action, up to and including termination of employment or contract, in accordance with applicable laws and organizational procedures.

Violations may also result in legal or regulatory consequences where applicable.

7.5. Continual Improvement

Performance, audit results, risk assessments, and management reviews shall be used to identify opportunities to enhance the effectiveness, suitability, and adequacy of this policy.